

The aerosol-cloud-water vapor nexus in the twilight zone

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Summary

Aerosols, clouds and water vapor constitute a complex intertwined system. The fate of each of its parts depends on the nonlinear interactions between itself and the other parts of the whole, atmospheric radiation and dynamics. As such, the synergies between aerosols and clouds, mediated by water vapor, are one of the least known climate forcing components in the Earth system (1). There's just no hope to adequately simulate the climatic radiative response of clouds (2) without first understanding cloud-aerosol-water vapor interactions at the microphysical level, at the spatial scales that really define their structure. Koren et al. (3) have dubbed the "twilight zone" the continuum that corresponds to the gradual transition between a cloudy environment to a region in the atmosphere where aerosol particles dominate. Lateral cloud detrainment provides a source of water vapor from the supersaturated cloud interior to its surroundings. Interacting with aerosol particles, water vapor can be adsorbed onto particle surfaces, making them swell and get activated to become cloud droplets, or else remain unactivated as haze in the atmosphere. Because there is no definite minimum limit on the amount of liquid water a cloud should hold, flimsy pockets of activated droplets can remain undetected by human eyes or by instruments, but still affect the atmospheric thermodynamic state. When solar radiation enters the stage the result is perceived as increased optical depth in the inter-cloud medium, due to enhanced photon scattering on gas molecules, aerosols, and subvisible clouds, as a consequence of the tridimensional structure of clouds.

We propose using a comprehensive instrumentation suite already in place at the University of Sao Paulo to study physical and optical properties of the aerosol-cloud-water vapor nexus. It includes a sunphotometer, a pyranometer, a multifilter rotating shadowband radiometer, lidar, multi channel all-sky cameras, integrated with polar and geostationary satellite retrievals and meteorological conventional observations (surface weather stations, sounding). **More importantly, this suite will be run by a team of experts and students under a new paradigm, seeking a comprehensive view of the twilight zone.** The analyses will be carried out in the Sao Paulo Metropolitan Area, a megacity comprising more than 21 million inhabitants. Local aerosol sources are dominated by particulate matter from traffic, either directly emitted or photochemically produced. Summers are wet and cloudy with low pollution levels, while winters are generally dry with few clouds, and severe atmospheric pollution spells. Up to the 60's or 70's Sao Paulo was known as the "drizzle land", from typical light precipitation events ubiquitous throughout the year. Climate change, pollution and disorganized urban sprawl have eclipsed our drizzle. Now this project vows to tackle the twilight between clouds and aerosols.

Research activities

Distinguishing clouds from atmospheric aerosols has long been considered an artificial enterprise. In 1986 Wielicki and Welch (4) have shown, from statistical analysis of satellite imagery, that no clear reflectance threshold can be defined to unambiguously estimate the cloud fractional cover in a given

area. Their results showed the reflectance distribution in a cloud field varied smoothly from a minimum detectable “clear-sky” level to a maximum representing the instrument saturation limit. Because there is no strict definition about cloud physical limits, the concepts of cloud fractional cover, or the distribution of cloud area size, are highly dependent on threshold limits defined from instrumental efficacy, or from a researcher’s particular assumptions. This phenomenon has been observed by different platforms, from aerial photography interpreted visually (5), in imagery acquired during the Apollo 9 space flight mission (6), on surface sun photometers (3), lidar (7) and spectrometer (8) measurements, in infrared satellite imagery (9), under coarse or fine spatial resolution detectors (10). Another approach could try defining cloud limits in terms of condensed water mass, but in that case too an arbitrary threshold is imposed (11) and so the original issue still stands. The so-called “twilight zone” (3), or the cloud-aerosol continuum (12), are the coined terms used nowadays to broadly represent the multiple thermodynamic states when transitioning between a cloudy environment and an aerosol-dominated scene, with spatial scales of tens of kilometers (11, 13). Measuring the radiation field in the twilight zone one detects an enhancement of optical depth in the vicinity of clouds. This is due to (a) 3D effects of photon scattering in cloud fields; (b) aerosol hydration (haze) in the vicinity of clouds; (c) undetected cloud pockets; (d) sensor blurring. Scattered photons enhance the observed optical depth in the vicinity of clouds from their bouncing off air molecules (Rayleigh scattering), water vapor, aerosols, nearby clouds and from the surface (14). Hydrated aerosol particles near clouds may swell from the absorption of water vapor, increasing the overall optical depth, without reaching the size threshold to become activated cloud droplets in the Köhler equation (15). Subvisible clouds are composed of feeble density parcels of activated cloud droplets, that do not reach the necessary number concentration to be detected by a given instrument (16–18). Sensor blurring can give rise to enhanced optical depth depending on each instrument’s channel point spread functions (19).

Despite all the amassed evidence for the existence of the twilight zone, currently all mainstream retrieval algorithms used to derive cloud or aerosol properties need to impose arbitrary thresholds to select ideal inversion conditions, represented by dichotomic states of pure “aerosol” or “cloud” data (20–25). It is estimated that the twilight zone corresponds to 20% of all detected pixels from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Radiometer (MODIS) satellite sensor, for which no retrievals are attempted (26). Aerosol radiative forcing estimates are often calculated by first applying cloud mask algorithms to ensure no cloud data is present (e.g. (27)). If a too stringent cloud mask is applied this will likely leave out of the calculation parts of the aerosol population and the twilight zone. Conversely, cloud radiative effects are often calculated by avoiding problematic cloud “border” pixels (e.g. (24)), ignoring that part of the radiation scattered or emitted by clouds originates from that region and from the continuum beyond the obvious cloud. Conceptual models used in radiative forcing estimations often bank on an oversimplified definition of planetary albedo, with a parcel due to the average cloud albedo and another, complementary part, due to clear-sky albedo (e.g. (28)). The implicit assumption is that aerosols and clouds can be clearly distinguished, their radiative properties calculated, and the final result is just a weighted average, according to their relative frequency of occurrence. Moreover, little is said about the role of water vapor that effectively links the inner cloud environment to its surrounding haze (unactivated humidified aerosols), or can undergo condensation/evaporation from droplets in nearby subvisible cloud filaments. Charlson et al. (12) evaluated that under conditions of low atmospheric aerosol loading the neglect of the cloud-aerosol continuum causes the magnitude of the aerosol indirect effect to be overestimated, and underestimated when aerosols are present in high concentrations. Clearly a new paradigm is needed to advance our knowledge about the twilight zone.

The very concept of twilight zone, with no clear boundaries between definitions of clouds and atmospheric aerosols, begs for a non-dichotomic analytical treatment. In partnership with the Geoprocessing and Environmental Modeling group, from Sao Paulo State University (UNESP), we propose tackling the twilight zone characterization under a fuzzy logic perspective. This approach

considers that a given element can belong simultaneously to multiple classes, with a varying level or degree of “membership” (29). Different types of membership functions can be used to portray how a given element (e.g. a data pixel) can be associated to a class, such as “cloud”, “aerosol”, “surface”, etc. Image processing using fuzzy logic can deal with issues such as finding edges, adjacency areas, measuring edginess, all of which can be interesting in analyzing twilight data. For the goals in this project, perhaps the most significant remark is that calculations can be performed on a subset, while keeping track of the uncertainty involved in its membership attribution to several categories (29). In principle this means we can work with different radiative properties for each type of element in the continuum, without the need for a priori binary classification. In this context, fuzzy logic seems like a very promising analytical tool to address the twilight zone.

The overall aim of this project is to derive optical and physical properties of the aerosol-cloud continuum. We propose using an observational component coupled to a modeling approach to achieve this goal. The University of Sao Paulo has a large instrumental infrastructure, already in place on campus, that is able to measure radiative properties in several wavelength ranges. The suite includes an Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET) 8-wavelength sunphotometer (30), a pyranometer and a multifilter rotating shadowband radiometer (31, 32) to measure spectral and broadband direct and diffuse solar radiation, lidar observations to measure vertical profiles of backscattered radiation (33), an all-sky (“fish-eye”) visible and infrared (ASIVA) camera (34) to measure calibrated radiances in 7 solar wavelength channels coincident with AERONET’s, and 4 thermal infrared bands. Combined with MODIS sensors aboard Terra and Aqua and GOES-16 observations, this panoply of instruments will be led by a team of expert scientists and students to characterize the inter-cloud environment with a new insightful perspective.

Our first step will be mapping isolines of constant intensity (counts) in sky camera imagery, or constant optical depth in satellite images. The spatial derivative of these variables is steeper near the edge of optically thick clouds, while at the same time one does not need to impose an arbitrary threshold to define cloudy pixels. From this we will calculate, for any point in a given scene, the distance from the nearest optically thick edge in the twilight, for each wavelength (D^e_λ). This is analogous to the distance from the nearest “cloud” in previous studies (3, 35), a key variable to characterize the continuum, but in our case the edge can be flexible and thus it refers not only to clouds, but rather to a subset of elements in the twilight. From the multispectral imagery we will also derive an analogous to the Angström exponent ($A^e_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2}$) to map how the elements in the twilight interact with solar radiation with an effective size parameter (8). In a field of broken shallow cumuli the thermal channels in the sky camera will be used to derive brightness temperature (T_B) maps in the twilight. Exploring $T_B \times D^e_\lambda \times A^e_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2}$ correlation maps will further help characterize the effective size parameter and spatial distribution of elements in the continuum. We are considering adding stereoscopic cameras set far apart on campus, observing the same cloud field, to also explore the twilight spatial distribution in the visible part of the spectrum. From the sunphotometer’s vantage point we will be able to characterize the twilight spatial distribution around AERONET’s sun-pointing observational axis.

3D scattering effects will be assessed in selected scenes using a Monte Carlo radiative transfer code, by calculating the difference in the radiation field with and without continuum elements above a specific optical edge (35–37), as a function of D^e_λ . Wen et al. (38) have adopted a simplified model to quantify the 3D enhanced Rayleigh scattering without using Monte Carlo simulations, but resorting to clear-cut definitions of cloudy vs. clear pixels we challenge. The 3D effects are more prominent in backscattered scenes observed from satellites than in surface data acquired by our instrumentation due to differences in the normalized phase function of aerosols and gas molecules (39). Boundary conditions for Monte Carlo simulations will be based on the radiative field measured by the

instrumental suite combining pyranometer, multi-filter shadow band radiometer and sunphotometer data. Using different wavelengths in deriving D_{λ}^e will make it possible to study and quantify the Rayleigh scattering component, separating it from scattering on aerosol particles, water vapor molecules, or from the surface.

Another key information to characterize the twilight zone is the distribution of water vapor around the continuum field (40). Usual AERONET sunphotometer and multi-filter water vapor content retrievals are based on direct sun measurements of attenuated radiation at the 940 nm channel, due to the strong water vapor absorption in this wavelength (41, 42). Accessing the raw multi-filter and sunphotometer data we can use measurements that automatic processing algorithms would discard due to the proximity of clouds. Comparing these measurements with our derivations for D_{λ}^e and $A_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2}^e$ will allow understanding the continuum effect on the radiometers' line of sight for water vapor retrievals. Another approach will be using lidar nighttime observations. Due to the strong solar background during daytime, most lidar systems can provide Raman backscattering only at night to assess the water vapor vertical distribution. These measurements can be made concurrent with radiosonde launches at 9 p.m. and 9 a.m. LT (0 and 12 UTC), from an airfield about 10 km far from the campus site, to provide columnar profiles of humidity measurements to calibrate lidar retrievals (43). With the co-located infrared sky camera we will be able to analyze the lidar water vapor profiles as a function of D_{λ}^e and $A_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2}^e$, where the wavelengths at night are restricted to the 4 thermal infrared channels in the sky camera. We will also explore other paths to seek a better understanding of humidification in the twilight zone. One possibility is exploring an oxygen A-band type of retrieval, but applying it to daytime downwelling radiation at the surface measured by the multi-filter unit and the sky camera, both at the 940 nm channel. The multi-filter data are recorded at about 1 min temporal resolution, thus allowing to explore variations in the radiation field due to the fast changing conditions in the twilight. When an optically thick passing cloud at the zenith humidifies the surrounding environment, the diffuse radiation field at 940 nm will suffer a decrease due to enhanced absorption at the humidified layer. The minimum air mass at the zenith will probably make this the best geometry for seeking this signal. The sky camera can provide context for this scenario, acquiring images at the same relevant wavelength. To our knowledge this strategy has never been tried before, and we hope it can contribute to a better understanding of water vapor in the aerosol-cloud continuum.

Schedule outlook

Our main objective is to derive optical properties in the twilight zone. Year one of our research, for which we seek seed funding, will focus on selected cases under simpler continuum conditions. For these cases we can validate our results against conventional sunphotometer, MODIS and GOES-16 aerosol retrievals. Once we map the key variables T_B , D_{λ}^e and $A_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2}^e$ that characterize the spatial distribution of continuum elements, we will employ multi wavelength (AERONET channels) all-sky camera imagery and data from other instruments in the suite to retrieve optical properties using AERONET-like algorithms (44–46). Cloudless dry winter days, often polluted, are a priori the best candidates for this initial phase. For those conditions, imagery analysis along the principal plane or along a circle of constant air mass, representing AERONET's almucantar scan, allows deriving the scattering phase function, single scattering albedo (45), complex refractive index and size distribution (44). Extinction optical depth will be derived from multi-filter measurements (31, 47). Because our methods are based on imagery and data acquired at a much higher frequency than AERONET's, we can rely on robust statistics to do the inversions. By validating the results with conventional products we will be able to assess our accuracy. Our team has been working for many years on retrievals of atmospheric properties, and thus we are very confident this first year phase can be accomplished under

very low risk. The results we will get at the end of the first year are already interesting: we will have established a full framework to derive robust, validated aerosol or haze properties from sky imagery, which in itself can be used in other analytical contexts. This will also jumpstart the next research phases seeking a deeper understanding of the continuum.

In the second year we will focus on developing the core modeling to assess 3D scattering effects in the vicinity of clouds in the twilight zone, as discussed above. We will also continue the measurements with the instrumentation suite to progressively move to more complex twilight cases. Situations with a few broken clouds will be studied by exploring inhomogeneities in the measured radiation field around optically thick clouds. These cases will likely fail to meet AERONET's algorithm requirements for aerosol inversions (48). In contrast, our approach deriving D^ϵ_λ will allow selecting image regions still available for optimum aerosol retrievals, and regions ever closer to the optically thick edge defined by D^ϵ_λ . We can only do this due to the investigative nature of this project, segregating statistically favorable cases, instead of running an operational product with much stricter goals. When selecting part of an image for analysis, as explained above, one restricts the number of scattering angles sampled for the inversions. This will increase the uncertainty level in the results, since less information is available to infer the retrieved quantities. In this scenario, the complex refractive index will likely be the most critical variable (49), and thus will require investigation to define what conditions allow for meaningful retrievals. At the end of the second year, we will get synergic results by combining 3D scattering modeling and the retrieved microphysical models adjacent to optically thick clouds.

The next three years will cover the remaining research topics discussed above. We foresee the full project will be carried out in five years, according to this outline:

Year 1: Deriving twilight zone key variables: distance matrix, Angström exponent, brightness temperature. First intensive operational period (IOP) during winter. Deriving twilight optical properties from imagery and other data. Validation of simple cases against AERONET, MODIS, GOES-16 retrievals.

Year 2: Deriving optical properties under more complex twilight cases. 3D Monte Carlo simulations. Assessment of 3D effects on the derived properties. Short IOPs in winter/spring.

Year 3: Second IOP in winter/spring. Analyses of water vapor retrievals. Correlation with key variables. Lidar data analysis.

Year 4: Developing fuzzy logic concepts to characterize radiative properties in the twilight zone. Short IOPs in winter/spring.

Year 5: Full derivation of microphysical models. Accuracy assessments. Archiving results for public access.

Budget estimate

We request seed funding for the first year of this project to cover the costs summarized in Table 1 below. The scholarship and grant costs correspond approximately to current standard values observed in Sao Paulo. A 10-day work trip to the US was included as a means for two Brazilian team members to be able to interact and plan research strategies with the American counterpart in the project.

Table 1. Budget estimate for the first year of project.

Item	Cost estimate, 1y (USD)
Ph.D. scholarship	9,700
Post-doc grant	22,700
10 day work trip to US for 2 team members	10,000
Computer and storage	2,600
Paper publishing charges	600
USP overhead estimate* (20% of total funding)	11,400
Total funding requested	57,000

*Depends on how the funds are transferred to Brazil, and how they are applied.

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